

Using Silyl Protecting Group to Enable Post-Deposition C-C Coupling Reactions of Alkyne-Functionalized N-Heterocyclic Carbene Monolayers on Au surfaces

Iris Berg^a, Lillian Hale^b, Mazal Carmiel-Kostan^a, F. Dean Toste^b and Elad Gross^{*a}

N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs) were functionalized with triisopropylsilyl (TIPS)-protected alkyne group and self-assembled on Au films to enable post-deposition functionalization by C-C coupling reactions. The TIPS group efficiently protected the alkyne and prevented its deprotonation during surface-anchoring of NHC. Sonogashira C-C coupling reactions were performed on the Au film in high yield following removal of the TIPS group, demonstrating that post-deposition coupling reactions can be employed to widen the chemical scope of surface-anchored NHCs.

The exceptional thermal stability and chemical versatility of surface-anchored N-heterocyclic carbenes (NHCs)^{1–5} provide unique opportunities to modify the surface properties by self-assembly of functionalized NHCs.^{1,3,9–11,15–18} Therefore, developing synthetic strategies for surface-anchoring of NHC ligands with various steric and electronic properties is essential for tailoring the impact of NHCs on surface properties. Generally, this has been achieved by synthesis of chemically-functionalized NHC ligands which were self-assembled on various surfaces.^{17,18}

A much more versatile approach envisions the formation of monolayers that contain a chemically-addressable group that can be modified through post-deposition reactions for tuning the surface properties. However, post-deposition functionalization reactions of NHC ligands have been mostly limited to functional group interconversions, such as oxidations and reductions, which greatly limits the scope of surface perturbations.^{19–21} Post-deposition functionalization reactions of the imidazole backbone have been reported;^{2,11,16,22} but functionalization at these surface-remote sites have limited impact on surface properties. Initial indications for the feasibility of post-deposition functionalization reactions of NHCs in proximity to the metal surface were recently demonstrated in metathesis and cycloaddition reactions,^{2,10} which showed the wide potential of this synthetic approach.

The above-mentioned limitations motivated us to consider a different strategy for expanding the scope of chemically-functionalized NHC monolayers. Our strategy is based on NHC functionalization with chemically-active groups that enables various post-deposition coupling reactions while using protecting groups to prevent undesired side reactions during surface-anchoring. The use of protecting groups, such as triisopropylsilyl (TIPS), to enable surface-anchoring of chemically-active ligands was previously demonstrated;^{23–26} In addition, Pd-catalyzed coupling reactions on self-assembled

monolayers was proven to be an efficient route for post deposition modifications.^{26–28} However, this strategy has not been previously leveraged to widen the chemical scope of surface-anchored NHCs. Herein, we demonstrate that post-deposition coupling reactions can be facilitated by surface-anchoring of alkyne-functionalized benzimidazolium iodide that was synthesized with TIPS-protection (Scheme 1a).

Scheme 1: (a) TIPS-protected alkyne-functionalized benzimidazolium iodide deposition on Au film. (b) TIPS deprotection (b) Sonogashira C-C coupling reactions.

N1s X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectrum of TIPS-protected benzimidazolium iodide revealed a signal that was fit by a single Gaussian and centered at 400.7 eV (Fig. 1a).²⁹ The XPS signature is comparable in its position and width to previously reported benzimidazolium salts.²² ATR-IR spectrum of the TIPS-protected benzimidazolium salt displayed a distinct peak at 2154 cm^{-1} , attributed to the $C\equiv C-Si$ vibration (Fig. 1b).³⁰

Figure 1: N1s XPS (a) and ATR-IR (b) spectra of TIPS-protected alkyne-benzimidazolium salt. N1s XPS and PM-IRRAS spectra of surface-anchored TIPS-protected NHC before (c and d, respectively) and following TIPS removal (e and f, respectively). The spectrum in f was increased by 6-fold for clarification.

N1s XPS spectrum of TIPS-protected NHC that was self-assembled on Au showed a similar peak pattern to that of the salt precursor (Fig. 1c). The center of the N1s XPS signal was detected at 400.5 eV, which is lower by 0.2 eV than the value measured for the benzimidazolium salt. The lower binding energy value is connected with neutralization of the positive charge of the nitrogen atom following surface complexation.²² The peak pattern of the surface-anchored NHC was similar to that of the imidazolium salt, which implies that deprotonation and surface anchoring did not induce noticeable chemical deformation.

Polarization-modulation Infrared reflection absorption spectroscopy (PM-IRRAS) measurement of surface-anchored NHCs in the spectral range of 2000-2250 cm^{-1} revealed three peaks, located at 2108, 2151 and 2189 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1d). The dominant peak at 2151 cm^{-1} was attributed to the $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ -Si stretching vibration and its position was comparable to the peak detected in the IR spectrum of the salt precursor (Fig. 1b).

In order to identify the source for the two additional IR features in the PM-IRRAS spectrum, a control experiment was conducted in which the TIPS-protected benzimidazolium salt precursor was deprotonated by KO^tBu and drop-casted on Si wafer. PM-IRRAS spectrum of the activated carbene on Si showed a single peak at 2151 cm^{-1} (Fig. S1). Thus, the two additional vibrational features that were detected at 2108 and 2189 cm^{-1} in the PM-IRRAS spectra (Fig. 1d) were induced following surface-anchoring of NHC on Au film. The peak at 2189 cm^{-1} was correlated to the $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ -Si vibration and was blue-shifted due to steric effects that led to weaker aromatic conjugation following surface anchoring.³¹ The lower-amplitude peak at 2108 cm^{-1} was associated with the vibration of the terminal alkyne³² and

its detection indicates that a fraction of the alkyne groups were deprotected during surface anchoring of NHCs. Raman and UV-Vis measurements were performed and validated the surface-anchoring of TIPS-protected NHCs (Fig. S2-S4).³³ The surface-anchored NHCs showed high thermal stability with no indication for desorption or deformation following annealing to 100 °C (Fig. S5).

Surface anchoring of non-protected alkyne-functionalized benzimidazole led to multilayer formation of NHCs on the Au film (Fig. S6). Multilayer formation was induced by deprotonation of the alkyne group, in addition to the imidazolium deprotonation, that led to self-polymerization of alkyne-NHC on the Au surface. Multilayer formation was observed despite attempts to decrease the salt concentration and the deposition duration, making the TIPS protection a crucial step for enabling monolayer formation of alkyne-functionalized NHC.

Deprotection of the alkyne groups was facilitated by immersing the Au films that were coated with TIPS-protected NHCs in tetrabutylammoniumfluoride (TBAF) solvated in THF (Scheme 1b). N1s XPS spectrum that was measured following deprotection did not show significant changes in the peak position and pattern (Fig. 1e), indicating that deprotection was not coupled with NHCs' deformation or desorption.

Quantitative analysis of the efficiency of TIPS removal was achieved by conducting electrochemical deprotonation of the terminal alkyne C-H groups of surface-anchored alkyne-NHC. Linear sweep voltammetry revealed an oxidation peak at 2.12 to 2.15 V, correlated to deprotonation of the alkyl group (Fig. S7). Integration of the oxidation peak indicated that the surface density of alkyne-NHC was $(1.3\pm 0.4)\cdot 10^{-11}$ $\text{mol}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$.

The relatively low surface density of alkyne-NHC can be correlated to the large size and asymmetric structure of TIPS-protected NHCs. These properties can induce strong interactions between surface-anchored NHC and the underlying metal atoms and hinder the formation of a packed monolayer. The low surface density, however, enabled on-surface coupling reactions with no steric limitations. The calculated surface density of alkyne-NHC was threefold higher than that of dinitrophenyl-functionalized NHCs on Au, which can be associated with the smaller size of alkyne-NHC.³⁴

Qualitative analysis of the effective removal of the TIPS group was identified by measuring the PM-IRRAS spectra of the sample following deprotection. A dominant peak was detected at 2108 cm^{-1} , correlated to the terminal alkyne (Fig. 1f). The ratio of the peak intensity at 2108 cm^{-1} versus the peak intensities at 2189 and 2151 cm^{-1} , correlated to TIPS-protected $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ bonds, was modified from 1:7 before deprotection to 1:1 following deprotection. The PM-IRRAS signal of surface-anchored NHCs deteriorated following deprotection (Fig. 1f), while the intensity of the N1s XPS signal was not noticeably changed (Fig. 1e). The lower overall IR intensity indicates that the NHCs accumulated a more flat-lying orientation following TIPS removal due to lower steric hindrance.^{35,36}

Following TIPS removal, the terminal alkyne group in surface-anchored NHC was utilized for facilitating Sonogashira coupling reactions using 4-fluoriodobenzene and 4-nitrophenyltriflate as coupling agents (Scheme 1c).³⁷ Sonogashira coupling reaction of alkyne-NHC and 4-fluoriodobenzene were performed (see supporting information for reaction details). The successful coupling reaction was validated by the detection of F1s XPS signal (Fig. 2).³⁸ The F1s XPS signal was not detected once the reaction was performed in the absence of surface anchored alkyne-NHCs (Supp. Info. Fig. S9), thus assuring that the XPS peak was not induced by physisorbed fluoriodobenzene.

Figure 2: F1s XPS signal of alkyne-NHCs on Au film before (i) and following (ii) Sonogashira coupling reaction with 4-fluoriodobenzene.

Following Sonogashira coupling reaction, an atomic percentage of 0.5% fluorine on Au film was calculated based on XPS. The atomic percentage of nitrogen, connected to the presence of surface-anchored NHCs and measured prior to the coupling reaction, was 0.8%. Since each NHC contains two nitrogen atoms for each fluorine, the XPS analysis suggests that the coupling reaction occurred efficiently.

The F1s XPS peak following the coupling reaction was detected at 684.2 eV, while the F1s XPS peak position of the precursor, 4-fluoriodobenzene, was located at 686.9 eV (Fig. S9).³⁹ The shift in the peak position suggests that a strong Au-F interaction induces a semi-ionic character of the fluorine, demonstrating the strong impact of surface proximity on NHCs properties. To widen the scope of Sonogashira coupling reaction of alkyne-NHC on Au films, an additional coupling reaction was conducted while using 4-nitrophenyltriflate as coupling reagent. N1s XPS spectrum of the deprotected alkyne-NHC,

prior to the coupling reaction, showed a single peak located at 399.5-402.5 eV, attributed to the nitrogen atoms of the imidazole ring (Fig. 3, spectrum i). Following coupling reaction with 4-nitrophenyltriflate, an additional high-energy peak (407.2 eV) was detected (Fig. 3, spectrum ii). This peak was not detected prior to the coupling reaction and was attributed to the nitro group of 4-nitrophenyltriflate.^{40,20}

Figure 3: N1s XPS signal of alkyne-NHCs SAM on Au film before (i) and following (ii) Sonogashira coupling reaction with 4-nitrophenyltriflate.

The significant increase in the low energy N1s XPS peak area (399-403 eV) following the coupling reaction was correlated to the presence of triethylamine residues that was added for activation of the coupling reaction. Control experiments of the coupling reaction with 4-nitrophenyltriflate, without surface-anchored NHCs, led to the exclusive detection of a low energy feature in the N1s XPS spectrum. This result assures that the high-energy peak in the XPS spectrum was not induced by physisorbed 4-nitrophenyltriflate residues (Fig. S10).

Quantitative analysis of the XPS data following Sonogashira reaction with 4-nitrophenyltriflate revealed that the atomic concentration of NO₂ on the Au film was 0.3%. The atomic concentration of nitrogen on the surface prior to the reaction was 0.8%. Since each NHC contains two nitrogen atoms for each nitro group, the XPS analysis indicates that this coupling reaction was performed as well with high efficiency. The vibrational signal of the terminal alkyne significantly decreased following the coupling reaction, thus indicating the coupling reaction efficiency (Fig. S11). Electroreduction measurements identified that the surface density of -NO₂ groups, following coupling reaction with 4-nitrophenyltriflate, was $(1.2 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^{-11}$ mol·cm⁻² (Fig. S12). This value is similar to the surface density of the alkyne moieties and indicates that effective coupling reaction was performed. The high coupling reaction yield affirms that coupling between two neighboring alkyne-functionalized NHCs did not occur following TIPS removal or following exposure to Sonogashira reaction conditions.

Atomic Force Microscopy measurements identified that the root mean square (RMS) surface roughness increased from 1.48 nm for the TIPS-protected NHCs to 3.40 nm following TIPS

removal (Fig. S13). The RMS roughness increased to 9.23 nm following coupling reaction with 4-nitrophenyltriflate. The gradual increase in surface roughness can be correlated to higher level of surface corrugation or to the presence of residues on the Au surface following post-deposition reactions. Water contact angle measurements showed that the Au surface became more hydrophobic following TIPS-removal and following coupling reactions (Table S1).

To conclude, in this work we demonstrate that post-deposition Sonogashira coupling reactions can be activated on Au surface by using self-assembled NHCs that were functionalized with a TIPS-protected alkyne group. TIPS protection prevented alkyne deprotonation and multilayer formation of NHCs on the Au surface. These results demonstrate that removable protecting groups provide access to surface-anchored NHCs with chemically-sensitive functional groups, enabling post deposition coupling reactions on Au films. The synthetic strategy presented herein enables the expedient preparation and diversification of versatile on-surface NHCs' functionalization for optimal tuning of surface properties.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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